

Review

Inland Water Transportation in Bangladesh: Prospects and Challenges

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Abstract: Inland Water Transportation has a vital role in Bangladesh's transportation of both goods and passengers. It is roughly 24,000 km from Bangladesh Rivers, lakes and canals, which collectively cover about 7 percent of its surface. A dynamic waterway network that links much of the city to its large size in the monsoon season. There is only 5968 km of rivers, lakes and canals and channels from 24,000 km away. Mechanized vessels are navigable throughout the monsoon season, which shrinks to 3,865 km. In the dry season, the IWT industry accounts for over 50 percent of cargo traffic and one-fourth of rail traffic (BIWTA, 17 apr, 2014). This paper discusses the possibilities and challenges of waterway transportation in Bangladesh's coastal area. The data have been collected from different journals, related books, publications, maritime institutions etc. Associated goals are: (i) to evaluate the region's potential to improve inland waterway transportation; ii) to assess the contribution of inland waterway transport to the transportation of passengers and freight; iii) to evaluate the effect of Inland waterway transportation on the economic improvement of Bangladesh and iii) to measure the outcome of inland waterway transportation on socio-economic progress (Owoputi Adetose Emmanuel, June 2018). In Bangladesh, however, there are more than 700 rivers, but the IWT sharing mode of transport is fragile compared to many other countries. In the Netherlands, the modal IWT share is 42 percent, France is 15 percent, Hungary is 15 percent, Germany is 14 percent, Belgium is 13 percent and the USA is 15 percent whereas in Bangladesh, only 7% (IWX, 2017). The core purpose of this study is to find out the necessity of Inland Water Transportation in terms of keeping continued human's daily activities as well as it is tried to show that there are considerable opportunities to meet up domestic transportation demand by waterways but that are not utilized. So, it should be made up the better policy to encourage private-public

participation (PPP) in the development of inland transportation sector in Bangladesh were suggested in this study

Keywords: *inland water; transportation; trade; challenges; river system; sustainable plan*

1. Introduction

Inland transportation is indeed one of the primitive secure transportation modes for travelers and freight in the economy and the environment. It is the only means of transportation and connections to public facilities in some areas. The sector involves single, no-motor attached ships to fully advanced pushers, running on waterways from smaller to large rivers. Inland waterways, especially in remote areas, play a crucial role in economic growth. However, the prospects of the future for this sector are highly dependent on the related provincial context such as geographical environment, roads, growth level and socio-economic condition. Lakes, canals, sea drains, deep sea, bays and protected coastal water areas are included in inland waterways. The citizen from the rural area and the low-income group generally use this way. And hence, the absence of rivers and inland waterway transportation, too dangerous to service by other means, many rural, underprivileged areas will be inaccessible or unavailable to reach their destination effectively (Owoputi Adetose Emmanuel, June 2018).

Bangladesh is a land of rivers where domestic transportation, inland water transportation (IWT) has occupied a vast mode of transportation for both individuals and cargos. In comparison with the other mode of transportation such as road and rail, inland waterways are the most comfortable transportation in Bangladesh. But not only a little attention was paid to the sector by the Bangladesh government but also limited allocation is given to its development. Besides, from this allocation significant portion is used to develop substantial routes for larger vessel and secondary rivers are given second preference where small ships (inland waterways) are operated. As a result, inland waterways remain underdeveloped. However, countries' ships, totaling several thousand conventional ships that have been utilized in inland and coastal waterways for hundreds of years and have played a crucial role as a rural mode of transportation of goods and carrying passengers. Though Inland water transportation has huge demand but terminal facilities are not sufficient. In rural areas, there are only “11 primary internal ports, 23 maritime terminals, island terminals, 133 launch stations and over 1,000 local landing points” (Bank, 2010). That is not enough as a query.

1.1 Objective of the research

The general objective of the research is to provide a clear vision of the existing operating system of inland and transport facilities in Bangladesh and its further development opportunities to fulfill the upcoming demand for waterways transportation both in the regional and international perspectives. The main objective of this study is as following: -

- To describe the pattern of cargo movements in the coastal zone of Bangladesh.
- Investigate the effect of waterway transportation on the socio-economic development of Bangladesh's coast.
- Investigate the problems that hinder the usage and spread of cargo transport on waterways.
- Explore the potential of inland waterways traffic in the coastal region of Bangladesh.
- Way of finding the best economic outcome utilizing Inland Waterway.
- And find out the possible barrier to mobilizing this sector.

1.2 The Inland Waterways of Bangladesh

Inland Waterways in Bangladesh

- The waterway in Bangladesh is classified into four hierarchical classes.
- The classification is made principally according to the Least Available Draft (LAD).
- The waterways Class I and II are major transport corridors where LAD of 2.1m to 3.6m.

IWT Classification	Length (km)	Depth (m)
Class-I	683	3.66-3.96
Class-II	1000	2.1-2.44
Class-III	1885	1.52-1.83
Class-IV	2400	Less than 1.52

Source: Department of Hydrography BIWTA

Figure-1: Classification of IWT of Bangladesh

1.3 The River System and Inland Water Transportation

The rivers of Bangladesh reflect both the physiography of the nation and the life of people. There are about 700 rivers in number which generally flow south. The more massive river provides the primary source of water for cultivation and the prime route of transportation. The rivers can be divided into five major categories. The Jamuna-Brahmaputra is 292 kilometers long and extends from northern Bangladesh to its confluence with the Padma. Originating as the Yarlung Zangbo Jiang in China's Xizang autonomous region and flowing from Indian's state of Arunachal Pradesh where it becomes known as the Brahmaputra. It receives waters from five major tributaries that total some 740 kilometers in length. At the point where the Brahmaputra meets the Tista River in Bangladesh and known as the Jamuna. The Padma-Ganges system is divided into two sections a 258-kilometer segment, the Ganges, which extends from the western border with India to its confluence with the Jamuna some 72 kilometers west of Dhaka, and ii) a 126 kilometers segment, the Padma, which runs from the Ganges-Jamuna where it joins it's called the Meghna River at Chandpur. The Padma-Ganges is the central part of a deltaic river system with hundreds of rivers and streams some 2100 kilometers in length, generally flowing east or west into the Padma. The third network is the Surma-Meghna system which occupied 669 kilometers. The fourth network is through the Bangladesh linear drains amounting to 1.5 kilometers. The fifth system is the Karnaphuli river system through Chittagong and Chittagong Hills which covered 420 kilometers.

In Bangladesh, there is about 24,000 km of lakes, spreading over 7 percent of the nation's soil. Out of this 24,000 km of rivers, streams and channels, only 5,968 km is navigable by autonomous boats during a flood time, which psychologists cross 3,865 km during a dry period. The Ganges, the Jamuna, the Padma, the Lower Meghna falls into the braided group, dubbed the braided one. In the Monsoon Seasons or the Heavy Periods of Water, their discharges fill the whole bed of the river, also Over-topping the banks and flooding nearby areas. In the winter seasons or the low water cycles, the winter seasons decreased discharges allow the river to bifurcate. A variety of branches that, in high water, meander banks used. Rivers such as the Surma, the Barak and the Atrai carry out gathering local discharges, catchments and feeding the major rivers.

Figure: 2River System of Bangladesh, Source: Meghna basin.jpg

On the other side, the rivers that branch out from larger rivers, e.g., the Lakhya and the Arial Khan river, which depend on the discharges obtained from the significant rivers called the tributaries, on the water levels. Generally, their variations in, offshoots, and outfalls are troublesome for navigation due to silt deposition and shoal formation induced in cross-sections to transitional shifts. The last river group known as the tidal rivers is mainly found in the southern part of the country and is dominantly tidal. Examples are the Pashur, the Karnaphuli, etc. Generally speaking, Bangladesh's rivers reflect a time of high water and low water flow. The short water cycle typically occurs from November to April each year, with the lowest water levels commonly occurring in the months of February-March. During this time, not only water levels but also shoals appear in the channels that limit smooth navigation. The classification of waterways according to their navigability, is also connected to the waterway's nature and features. With a minimum LAD of 3.6 meters and 2.1 meters respectively. Both operating and proposed marine ports are connected by inland waterway transport to the major hinterland (K.R. Hasan, 2016).

2. Procedures and Materials

This research adopts the primary and secondary research methodologies, and the qualitative methods of primary research and literature review techniques for secondary research are merged.

In this study, 350 copies of questionnaires were given to seven government departments and 410 copies of questionnaires were given to individuals in two formats of questionnaires. Both mathematical methods, analytical and inductive, have been used in this study. Plots, graphs, maps and key metrics are the descriptive tools used. The analytical component, step, and multiple regression models were the constructive analysis used in this study. Through this report, I have tried to figure out the overall view and relevance problem of Bangladesh's inland water transportation in terms of economic growth.

3. Prospects

Bangladesh is a country of the river where the inland water transport network is one of the most significant waterways in the world, with 1,000 landing points and 21 inland waterway terminals, stretching 24,000 kilometers. Since November 2013, the Inland Terminal of Pangaon has been occupied with 55,000 sq m of ownership yards, 2400 TEUs, controlling the cap and two piers. Around 3 million TEUs are handled annually by the Port of Chittagong and 80 percent of it is destined for Dhaka and just 10 percent by rail for Dhaka. A key factor in the growth of South Asia (SA) is port-led maritime economic development (Rakibul, Kazi , Wei, 2020).

At present, the holder can be transported via inland courses at a less expensive pace. If the framework for IWT cooperation is made severe and significant as indicated by the Asian advancement bank survey, Bangladesh will lift its GDP by 1 percent, while unfamiliar trade by 20 percent. There are over 10,000 inland vessels, 75 seaside vessels and about 6,500 inland vessels registered with a branch of distribution, and almost every one of these vessels operates within Bangladesh ((Retd.), 2019). In Bangladesh, important routes for inland water transports are Narayanganj, Chandpur, Bhairab, Barisal, Chittagong, and Khulna. Around 35 to 45 thousand people use this way daily. Currently, about 88 million passengers and 58 million tons of cargo are carried by IWT every year. So, for national economic growth, it is the best transport way that has substantial prospects for increasing GDP and creating a job market for an unemployed person.

3.1 Prospect of passenger movement

In 1970 Bangladesh, inherited five inland river ports. As the newly developed nation was focused on rebuilding its war loss, growth and economic activities intensified. As a result, the flow of passengers and freight improved. To satisfy demand, several new ports have grown and

today there are around 23 officially gazette important inland river ports of Bangladesh. They are geographically dispersed throughout the country and effectively provide landing and handling facilities for citizens especially those living in remote rural areas and coastal islands without land access.

As these river ports are the critical point of origin and destination the flow of travelers through them gives an indicator of their current activities. Current figures show a rise of 0.05% which is not inspiring. The critical reasons for this can be traced to continuous infusion of vast sums of capital resulting in i) rapid development of the urban and rural road network (ii) the introduction of a significant number of foreign-exchange road vehicles (iii) negligence of the preservation and service of the countries naturally developed inland waterway transport infrastructure and (iv) customer choice of travelers over quicker and more time-saving cars. This resulted in travelers being diverted to other modes of transport. However, an indicative projection of 332 million passengers in 2020-21 is made in a recent report by the Asian Development Bank.

3.2 Prospect of cargo movement

According to the below table, the growth rate of cargo handling was high (16.18%) in the 2017-2018 financial year but after that, it is reduced by 3.38 % only in 2020. It is happened due to COVID 19 that estimated. Before 2019 the growth rate of cargo handling was increasing gradually where Inland cargo handling holding a large portion of economic growth.

Financial Year	Import (in metric tons)	Export (in metric tons)	Inland (in metric tons)	ICD (in metric tons)	ICT (in metric tons)	Grand Total (in metric tons)	Growth (%)
2014-2015	48941406	5839986	6469673	474800		61725865	15.21
2015-2016	58324786	5971634	6366607	493360		71156387	15.28
2016-2017	66464285	6709759	6330639	477836		79982519	12.40
2017-2018	78050447	6997465	7429082	446234		92923228	16.18
2018-2019	82939731	6846406	7761749	515245	177524	98240655	5.72
2019-2020	87275248	6645145	6965977	489124	189777	101565272	3.38

Table-1: Cargo Handling Including Inland & ICD (in metric tons) Source: CPA BD

Transportation of bulk freight POL and containers is beneficial to Inland Waterways. It is cheaper, more fuel consuming less polluting, and environmentally sustainable. In Bangladesh, it has additional benefits that it creates jobs for the middle-class people and is directed towards supporting the underprivileged and more impoverished parts of the population. The estimated growth rate of the cargo movement in recent years is around 10% and the approximate traffic forecast for 2020-21 is approximately 58 million tons (Khan E. P., 2013).

3.3 India-Bangladesh Trade

The bilateral trade between India and Bangladesh was started after the liberation from Pakistan. Bangladesh was needed consumer goods after independence which came from India in 1971. Bangladesh also began to free up its economy shortly afterward. The nation adopted economic reforms in 1982. This led to rising Indian exports to Bangladesh. In the 1980s basic goods including leather rubber paper and chemicals were the principal exports from Bangladesh. Gradually, the list has developed and today, Bangladesh exports pharmaceuticals textiles iron and steel raw jute jamdani, sarees, health instruments and accessories for clothes. In India, these have found a growing demand.

On the other hand, Bangladesh imports from India, including food seeds cloth cotton thread machines equipment glass and glassware ceramics and machines and coal. The study of the trade relationship between India and Bangladesh reveals that recurrent encounters in Bangladesh are imbalance in bilateral exchange in her trade with India (Zahoor Ahmad Rather, Dr. Deepika Gupta., 2014) “India is the third-largest trading partner of Bangladesh but in case of imports it is in second. Bangladesh on the contrary remains in the top 10 among India’s export destinations as well. Which is nearly 90 percent of overall trade from India to Bangladesh (DCCI 2017) and about 10 percent trading from Bangladesh to India (DGCIS Website 2017)” (Khandaker Rasel Hasan1M Ziauddin Alamgir, 2017). These indicate the prospects of future trade between India and Bangladesh. Most of this trade happened from the west- Bangle to Bangladesh which is very near to the Bay of Bangle. In 2019 trade between these two countries amounted to USD 8895.6 million and about 40 percent of these transactions were carried out by the IWT (Khandaker Rasel Hasan, 2018).

Figure-3: India-Bangladesh Trade (FY2015-FY2019) Source: EPABB

3.4 Environment Friendly

Sea transport is considerably more climate-friendly and environmentally friendly than road transport. The goal of the EU is to transfer 50% of freight transport from road to rail by 2050. According to a study, Norwegian officials have also set ambitious targets for lowering greenhouse gas emissions including reducing emissions from non-quota-controlled sectors to 40 percent of production where transportation is the key source of emissions.

The "Weather Research Effect of Goods Transition from Road to Shipping" (DNV-GL 2016) estimates that almost 30% of all freight transport shipped from Europe to Norway by road could be moved to shipping. The National Transport Plan (NTP) for 2018-2027 suggests that 5-7 million tons of goods will be converted to shipping currently transported by sea. (Color Line).

Mode	Road	Rail	Coastal Shipping
Emission in g CO2 equivalent/ton-km	64%	28%	15%

Source: Report titled "Building India: Transforming the Nation"

Table-2: Amount of CO2 emission in road rail and waterway

It is clear from the above table that the emission of CO₂ of coastal shipping is very low in amount comparing with Road and Rail transportation. By coastal shipping, 15% of CO₂ is emitted whereas both rail and road are emitted 28% and 64%. The goal of the framework of the Green Economy is to reduce the Carbon footprint of methods of growth. The IWT is a highly fuel-efficient mode of transportation to control carbon emission. It is estimated that one liter of fuel will hold 24 tons /km of freight by road 85 tons/km by rail and 105 tons/km by waterways (IWAI-2008/2009) (Nagabhatla & Jain, 2013).

4.Challenges

Unfortunately, owing to the continued low priority provided by policymakers to inland waterways in contrast to other competitive surface modes, the Inland Water Transport (IWT) system is not as well built in Bangladesh as the Roads and Railways. Indeed, inland waterways have experienced a steady decline not only in terms of navigable length but also in terms of quality of service and safety standards.

The explanation for this is obvious. Compared to competitive modes (Roads and Railways), the vastly inadequate allocation of funds in construction plans annual development projects and annual tax budgets stretches money so widely that even current infrastructure does not attract sufficient repair and maintenance consideration. The following two tables address the problem articulately and do not require further explanation.

The domestic water transportation industry in Bangladesh is comparatively established comparing with other major transportation due to a matrix of natural causes and policy discrepancies. In the Bangladesh field of Inland Water Transport general issues or challenges in the Inland Water Transport Sector are categorized as technical, regulatory geo-political economic channel shifting and integrated development issues. (Praveen S, 2015).

4.1Technical Challenges

The lack of sufficient navigation facilities is one of the most significant problems facing this business.

4.1.1Sediment Problem

The Basin of Bengal is the world's biologically productive and geographically youngest river area. (D. K. Datta, 1999)) which was created by alluvial sediment deposition from the systems

of the Ganges Brahmaputra and Meghna rivers. This basin forms the world's most significant soil dissemination scheme such as repeated soil deposition lifts the ground level near to the water bank retaining the ground deep between the two rivers. This is called the "beel," which is a low floor then surface. A Coastal Basin is a depressed low-lying area or beel adjacent to tidal sediment-laden rivers (Md. Sharif Imam Ibne Amir, 2013)

Figure 4: Sediment Problem of Mohananda River (Source: thedailystar.net)

The figure shows that because of the enormous amount of sediment, the river bed is getting up of the Mohananda river. As a result, the river is going to be filled up by sand. Moreover, human wastages like kitchen dust plastic bottle and polythene dust from the market and other places are thrown into the water that is one of the significant causes of river sediment.

4.1.2 Inadequate depth

Significant portions of the rivers of Bangladesh are not deep enough for commercial freight movements. Inadequate deepening sufficient depth or less usable depth is needed to allow the accessibility of larger ships which is necessary to make the domestic water transportation system economically viable by capital expenditure. Besides, rivers in Bangladesh (particularly in the north-western plains) face serious sediment problems during the year. The river bed rises and hampers the influx of freight during the months of the monsoon. Though the Bangladesh government has taken the initiative for river dredging to increase navigation through 'Delta plan 2020-2021' costing Tk 1923 corer, it is needed another year to complete the work estimated by BIWTA.

4.1.3 Insufficient Air Draft

According to research, various bridges with vertical direction height block the navigation of larger inland waterway ships such as Third Buriganga Bridge (Bangladesh Inland Water

Transport Authority (BIWTA team of hydrograph experts) assessed both the water level of the river and the bridge distance from the water level and found that it was just 13.2 meters instead of the required 15 meters (Khan M. A., 2009). Padma Bridge (at Mawa point Bangladesh Bridge Administration's required 15.5 meters of horizontal visibility while 11.1 meters of vertical clearance and at Janjira point the horizontal support was 13.9 meters instead of 15.5 meters and the vertical clearance was 5.3 meters instead of 5.7 meters) (Akhter, 2020). Similarly, several other bridges in Bangladesh can not be used for freight transport owing to an air draft limit.

4.1.4 Inadequate Dredging Service

The emerging state of demands on waterways a famous service in dredging. The Cabinet is trying to hit the limit in countering this too problem. Nevertheless, the shipping industry in Bangladesh has been notably established in a biased way focusing more on the roads and the highways department (RHD). Thus, the investment allocation for the growth of the IWT does not include concern roads and highways. It is satisfactory in 79.64 percent of the overall ADP for 2007-08 was distributed to RHD while only 1.37 percent was given to IWT. And in the same year, 33.5 percent of its money was invested by BIWTA on works associated with dredging. The repentant reality is that 56% of this money was spent on sustaining channel dredging and ferry station which currently the RHD operates leaving the primary streams in an insignificant condition (Hossain, Awal, & Das, 2014).

4.2 Financial Challenges

4.2.1 Investments by Governments

Investments have been made in the inland water transport infrastructure business about road and rail transport. While substantial focus has been put on implementing highway and rail infrastructure plans over the next five years, the inland water transport market has been ignored. As a result, public spending on inland water transport has been well below the rate reached by other forms.

4.2.2 Investments from private firms

As a policy move, the prospect of private sector investment in the growth maintenance and regulation of some parts of inland waterways can be discussed in the same way as other transport

sectors such as road and metro rail (Praveen S, 2015). The investment of private firms is not sufficient as much as needed. The government has to come forward to make them convince and give many facilities and security.

5. Channel Shifting

“In Bangladesh, Padma is one of the major rivers and satellite images show that it has been growing in size changing in shape and changing in location for at least the last 30 years. In India, it forms at the intersection of the Ganges and Jamuna Rivers, then merges with the Meghna River and finally the Bay of Bengal. Millions of people depend on the Padma for agriculture which means that they have to adapt every day to changes in the river's 130-kilometer (75-mile) coastline. In recent decades various farm residences and livelihoods have been lost or removed due to riverbank erosion. Hundreds (sometimes thousands) of miles of land explode and fall into the Padma River each year. More than 66000 hectares have been lost since 1967 (256 square miles)” (Earth observatory, 2018).

Figure-5: Channel Shifting from 1988 to 2018 of Padma River

source: (Earth observatory, 2018)

6.Recommendation

- Setting up more inland port and landing station.
- Increase depth and air draft in terms of making bridge.
- Improving the navigability.
- Controlling the garbage and plastic products thrown into the river.

- Skilled navigators should be employed.
- Sustainable plan should be taken.
- Infrastructure development of launch/ ferry station with modern facilities.
- Compulsory training arrangement for all crews and officers should be taken.
- Safety equipment such as a life Jacket Life raft ring buoy must be available in the vessel.

7. Conclusion

It can be concluded that at this moment, Bangladesh needs much awareness and broaden the horizon towards utilizing inland waterways and bring a positive change in socio-economic growth in the life of the people of Bangladesh. Water surrounds the three parts of the country and it has many rivers around the cities. Inland water transportation can be one of the potential transportation ways to achieve sustainable development goals. This study attempted to find the present scenario of waterways of Bangladesh. From the analysis, we found that the use of rivers carrying in both passenger and cargos is increasing. It's a positive sign. However, the frequent flood and natural calamity in Bangladesh are damaging roads and infrastructure development, such as the launch station ferry station terminal and jetty that was hampering the daily economic activities in the rainy season. Without well-trained, skilled, and transparent human resources and infrastructure development dynamic and populous transportation are impossible for any country. So, developing inland water transportation can contribute much to the economic development of Bangladesh if we can use this transportation route entirely.

The government should take the future long-term policy for the success of the inland water transportation system, which may focus on structural development establishing modern terminal transparency in administration holistic approach of safety first and training the young generation.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declare no conflicts of interest

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